

ExPaNDS Guidance Note:

Key Recommendation Elements for FAIR Photon and Neutron Data Management

The common metadata framework for FAIR data generated in Photon and Neutron (PaN) facilities

Data management at PaN facilities

Data produced at PaN facilities follow a life cycle consisting of different steps during which annotations (metadata) are produced to provide contextual information in order for this data to be easily found, accessed, made interoperable and reused (thereby complying with the **FAIR principles**¹). As shown in the high-level view of the (meta)data flow in PaN facilities depicted in Figure 1, the **metadata catalogue** is the central element from which datasets can be browsed directly by facility users, or indirectly by non-expert users via other platforms such as those provided by the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). Once a suitable dataset has been found, the catalogue should provide a gate to send data together with a set of parameters to a **data analysis portal**. Thus, in order for all these processes to happen, the question arises of which metadata to collect and which standards and formats are the most appropriate to structure them.

Figure 1: A high-level view of the (meta)data journey at PaN facilities. The flows of data and aggregated metadata are respectively shown using continuous and dotted lines.

¹ Wilkinson, M., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. et al. The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. Sci Data 3, 160018 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

Aim of metadata framework

The aim of the metadata framework within the ExPaNDS project is to suggest a common structure for the body of metadata that must accompany the acquisition of experimental data. The work developed in ExPaNDS deliverables 2.2² and 2.7³, and summarised hereafter encompasses the following points

1. The structure and the nature of the fields that constitute the metadata framework for FAIR data.
2. A discussion about the implementation details of this framework given the variety of infrastructures present in the different PaN facilities.

Description of the framework

The metadata framework adopts the temporal structure developed in earlier work in deliverable D6.1. of the PaNdata-ODI project⁴, termed the **PaN data continuum**. This structure reflects the lifecycle of an experimental session at a generic facility. The different steps identified in this structure are: **proposal**, **approval**, **scheduling**, **experiments**, **storage**, **processing**, **analysis**, and finally **record/publication**. An illustration of this process showing the different types of data produced at each step is illustrated in Figure 2.

Fig. 2: the data/metadata value stream (from ExPaNDS D2.2)

² Salvat, D., Gonzalez-Beltran, A., Gözrig, H. et al. (2020). ExPaNDS D2.2: Draft Recommendations for FAIR Photon and Neutron Data Management. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4312825>

³ Soler, N., McBirnie, A., Gonzalez-Beltran, A., Vukolov, A., Minotti, C., et al. 2022, July 7. Final recommendations for FAIR Photon and Neutron Data Management. <https://zenodo.org/record/6799105>.

⁴ Matthews, B. et al. (2012). *Model of the data continuum in Photon and Neutron Facilities*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3897190>

Types of data

While the following definitions may vary depending on the technique under consideration, the different types of data generated at PaN facilities can be classified as follows:

Raw data: the data collected from experiments performed on facility instruments that are considered as the source for any further analysis / processing.

Derived / Processed Data: data as a result of reduction or processing of the raw data during the Experimental lifecycle. Note: some may identify the Processing Data step as part of Analysis Data.

Analysed Data: data results from the analysis of either raw, processed or derived data (generally involving scientific input). This newly created data is also a candidate for the record/publication process.

Curated data: resulting from the process of making data FAIR.

Graphical summary of the framework

The metadata framework, summarised graphically in Figure 3⁵ represents an ideal “recipe” supporting the implementation of metadata collection strategies at PaN facilities. Metadata fields are proposed for each step of the PaN data continuum, together with an indicator derived from the FAIR Data Maturity Model⁶ as well as to which FAIR principles the metadata record contributes to. The three levels of importance defined by the FAIR data maturity model are:

- **Essential (P1):** such an indicator addresses an aspect of the utmost importance to achieve FAIRness under most circumstances, or, conversely, FAIRness would be practically impossible to achieve if the indicator were not satisfied.
- **Important (P2):** such an indicator addresses an aspect that might not be of the utmost importance under specific circumstances, but its satisfaction, if at all possible, would substantially increase FAIRness.
- **Useful (P3):** such an indicator addresses an aspect that is nice-to-have but is not necessarily indispensable to achieve FAIRness.

⁵ Soler, N., McBirnie, A., Gonzalez-Beltran, A., Vukolov, A., Minotti, C., et al. 2022, July 7. Final recommendations for FAIR Photon and Neutron Data Management. <https://zenodo.org/record/6799105>.

⁶ FAIR Data Maturity Model Working Group. (2020). *FAIR Data Maturity Model. Specification and Guidelines (1.0)*. <https://doi.org/10.15497/rda00050>

Fig.3 the metadata framework in the PaN data continuum. Arrows on the left side symbolise the possibility of going back and forth between different steps.

The definition of each of those fields is given in ExPANDS D2.2⁷ chapter 5.

Use cases

Various role-centric use-case scenarios for the use and reuse of FAIR data have been identified, as shown in Table 1.

User type	Use case
User Scientist	Data Analysis immediately after the experiment
User Scientist	Validating measurement
User Scientist	Finding and re-analysing measurement data with other algorithm after a long period of time or third-party
User Scientist	Reusing data for simulations (i.e. comparing experiment with theory)
User Scientist	Reproducing experiments (with similar sample)
Instrument Scientist	Advising/Supporting visiting scientists in relation to their experiments and setting up an instrument.
Instrument Scientist	Preparing and improving instrument and instrument setup to allow better experimental measurement.
Data Managers	Tracking data usage using both global and internal persistent identifier (PID)
Data Managers	Registering a Persistent Identifier (PID) for long-lasting reference of the data for future links to publications.
Data Managers	Archiving data for long term usage
Data Managers	Making research data available to PaN Search API
Data Managers	Making research data available to EOSC Project
Administrators	Needing to write reports
Publishers	Acting as agents in assessing completeness of metadata, verification and peer review of results.
Publishers	Controlling the authorship of the last derivatives of the data
Scientist Reviewer	Peer-reviewing data in relation to a research paper
Funders	Controlling the RIs policies of financial activities.
Funders	Acting as arbiters from the RI side against Principal Investigators.

Table 1: use-cases for data reuse

⁷ Salvat, D., Gonzalez-Beltran, A., Görzig, H. et al. (2020). ExPaNDS D2.2: Draft Recommendations for FAIR Photon and Neutron Data Management. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4312825>

Roles and information systems

Within all the use cases, we have identified three types of roles which can be played by different people within the lifecycle, depending on the step we are actually analysing. In all the cases, we identify the following generic roles:

- **Data Producer** (e.g. User Scientists, Instrument Scientists): should provide information that will help define the context of the experiment (e.g. description of the study, definition of the sample). In many cases, this context information is available before the experiment is performed.
- **Data Consumer** (e.g. Scientific Validator, Someone who reuses the data): Whoever uses the data to either validate the scientific results, reproduce the analysis, or reprocess the dataset for new scientific results.
- **Data Manager** (e.g. Data Management role: Archivist, Librarian): validates the integrity of the data (e.g. curation, custody).

we identify as many information system types as roles:

- **Data Production Systems:** Proposal systems, which are used to submit experimental cases; acquisition systems, which are used to collect data and metadata from measurements. Data Consuming Systems: Systems for data accessing, visualisation or downloading. Data Management Systems: Systems for data processing, analysis, etc.
- **Data Consuming Systems:** Systems for data accessing, visualisation or downloading.
- **Data Management Systems:** Systems for data processing, analysis, etc.

Modalities of implementation of the Common Metadata Framework for FAIR data across PaN facilities

This part reviews current practices and tools for metadata capture, storage and exposure and highlights the commonalities of the framework with other initiatives and tools developed inside and outside ExPaNDS. In relation to all these aspects, we make a series of recommendations, which fall under **three broad themes**:

1. FAIR metadata within PaN RIs
2. FAIR PaN metadata in the EOSC
3. Derived data provenance and preservation

Theme 1: FAIR metadata within PaN RIs

1.1 General consideration

Using the FAIR metadata framework as a basis, carefully design the metadata acquisition plan for a particular instrument through **dialogue between the different stakeholders** (instrument scientists, users, data acquisition and management staff). Metadata records heavily depending on users (e.g. calibration, sample, experimental notes) should be given special attention.

Across the experimental lifecycle within PaN RIs, there are **multiple information sources** – both human and machine – that play a role in metadata production and collection. In many cases, it is important that these sources interact and integrate within and across the various stages of the experimental lifecycle.

Implement a robust sample **metadata database system** (as a unique source) integrated in the other data management resources of the facility.

Implement and promote the use of **electronic logbooks / notebooks**. A system of information tagging would facilitate the parsing of the different types of metadata mentioned by machines.

Favour the use of **persistent identifiers (PIDs)** for data, people, instruments and samples when possible.

Agree on and **control the visibility level of each metadata record**, in agreement with the embargo period duration.

Each step in the experimental lifecycle produces specific metadata. Metadata will be stored in files and exposed in the metadata catalogue. Exposition and storage should ideally be made using their **appropriate metadata schemata**. Avoid dependency on a unique format when aggregating (meta)data in files and data catalogue. One metadata standard or file format might not be enough to express the information to be stored and exposed.

1.2 Sample metadata

Sample information is crucial for both findability and reusability of the data. Obtaining an accurate record of sample composition, state and **provenance**, largely relies on the user and therefore poses a particular challenge. Several strategies can be implemented to mitigate this issue:

- Extract information from the proposal: Samples and substances must be declared in order to validate the safety of an experiment.
- Provide a sample-description interface and database, that helps the user **centralise** information. This would ideally be coupled to the proposal system and to the sample tracking system to have a unique source of information.
- Reward users for entering FAIR sample information

1.3 Usage of electronic logbooks / notebooks

An ergonomic electronic logbook/notebook annotation system, tightly coupled to the user's data stored in facilities, allows rich metadata to be captured (annotations, system logs, images etc.). It reduces the risk of (meta-)data loss and ensures better preservation and reusability. We therefore recommend their implementation and promotion among users.

Independently of the e-logbook implementation, we propose that facilities implementing electronic notebooks adopt a harmonised approach for tagging both user and acquisition system information based on the "Experiment" part of the framework and automatically extract them in order to inject them into the data catalogue. This system would provide a convenient way of collecting essential information from the users while the experiment is ongoing, thereby releasing them from the burden of having to enter the information later through distinct interfaces.

By essence, electronic notebooks are based on time-stamped events, which is not suited to provide complementary information about the experiment as a whole. A better, alternative approach would be to use a sample-focused electronic laboratory notebook, easily editable by the users before, during and after the experiment, (ideally coupled to the sample tracking system). As mentioned in Günther et al. 2021⁸, a system based on Jupyter notebooks could also serve this purpose by allowing to combine code, notes and images in a single file.

1.4 The NeXus format

We recommend the use of NeXus/HDF5 as a self-contained and self-descriptive format to store data and scientific metadata, facilitating data exchange and reuse. Administrative metadata can to a certain extent also be stored using NeXus. Suggestions of **mapping tables** from the framework to NeXus base classes are available in ExPaNDS D2.7 (chapter 4) and are reproduced in the appendix for convenience. Finally we also want to highlight the use of **NeXus terminology in data catalogues**, providing a single controlled vocabulary of

⁸ Günther et al. (2021). *FAIR meets EMIL: Principles in Practice*. ICALEPCS2021, Shanghai, China. <https://doi.org/10.18429/JACoW-ICALEPCS2021-WEBL05>

NeXus terms (base class and field names) by flattening and joining the separate namespaces of base classes in a consistent and reversible manner⁹.

Theme 2: FAIR PaN metadata in the EOSC

2.1 Findability via the common search API

The [common search API](#)¹⁰ (also called the PaN search API) offers the possibility to query a data catalogue or even several of them in multiple facilities. The supported metadata fields have been agreed during the course of the ExPaNDS and PaNOSC projects (shown in Figure 4). Those fields can be directly mapped to the metadata framework presented in Figure 3 (see table 4 of ExPaNDS D2.7¹¹), however not all fields can be queried yet and the framework can thus serve as a basis to extend the number of fields searchable by the API.

Fig.4 the common search API data model (from PaNOSC D3.1¹²)

⁹ Collins, Ramos, da G., Iyayi, Görzig, Beltrán, G., et al. 2021, June 4. ExPaNDS ontologies v1.0. <https://zenodo.org/record/4806026>

¹⁰ <https://github.com/panosc-eu/search-api/>

¹¹ Soler, N., McBirnie, A., Gonzalez-Beltran, A., Vukolov, A., Minotti, C., et al. 2022, July 7. Final recommendations for FAIR Photon and Neutron Data Management. <https://zenodo.org/record/6799105>.

¹² Ashton, Ramos, D. G., & Gonzalez-Beltran. 2020, October 31. Report on status, gap analysis and roadmap towards harmonised and federated metadata catalogues for EU national Photon and Neutron RIs. <https://zenodo.org/record/4146819>.

As the PaN search-API requires an implementation for each data catalogue flavour (e.g. ICAT, SciCat), we reference here links that include **mappings**, either explicit or implicit, between the PaN search-API and its ICAT^{13 14 15} and SciCat^{16 17 18} implementations. Those mappings are fundamental for the users to query different flavours of data catalogues, since ICAT and SciCat search-API are needed to translate the fields queried from the user to the actual metadata fields in the data catalogue. We think the references serve the purpose better, as they dynamically incorporate any future change and keep track of the changes that might occur in the mapping. More details are available in the ExPaNDS deliverable D2.7 and D3.3¹⁹.

2.2 EOSC data indexing and discovery services

EOSC indexing and discovery services such as B2FIND and OpenAIRE offer the means to make PaN datasets more findable by non-expert users (outside the PaN domain). To enable these generic tools to harvest our metadata, it is important that PaN RIs provide:

- 1) OAI-PMH endpoints;
- 2) mappings of our metadata to the metadata schemas used by the EOSC services.

Regarding metadata mapping, it is important to bear in mind the purpose of services such B2FIND and OpenAIRE. Such tools are aimed at cross-domain discovery; they are not designed to capture the full domain-specific richness that is possible using the ExPaNDS metadata framework.

It is not necessary nor should we expect to map every aspect of our framework to the metadata schemas of the cross-domain EOSC services. However, to meet the primary purpose of the EOSC discovery tools, it is important that the information we make available through B2FIND and OpenAIRE is: 1.) sufficient for the initial enquiries of a non-domain specialist; and, 2.) able to point that user to where they can find further Details.

Given the nature of the B2FIND and OpenAIRE metadata schemas, it is not possible to map every metadata type found in the more extensive ExPaNDS metadata framework to these schemas. Additionally, multiple ExPaNDS metadata types may map to a given

¹³ <https://github.com/ral-facilities/datagateway-api/#mapping-between-panosc-and-icat-data-models>

¹⁴ https://github.com/ral-facilities/datagateway-api/blob/main/datagateway_api/search_api_mapping.json.example

¹⁵ https://github.com/ral-facilities/datagateway-api/blob/main/datagateway_api/src/search_api/panosc_mappings.py

¹⁶ <https://github.com/SciCatProject/panosc-search-api/blob/master/common/mappings.js>

¹⁷ https://github.com/SciCatProject/panosc-search-api/blob/master/common/filter_mapper.js

¹⁸ https://github.com/SciCatProject/panosc-search-api/blob/master/common/response_mapper.js

¹⁹ Soler, N., McBirnie, A., Gonzalez-Beltran, A., Vukolov, A., Minotti, C., et al. 2022, July 7. Final recommendations for FAIR Photon and Neutron Data Management. <https://zenodo.org/record/6799105>.

element/property in the B2FIND and OpenAIRE metadata schemas, meaning a one to one mapping is not always possible.

As an example, we provide some initial guidelines on how ExPaNDS metadata types for a raw dataset could be mapped to the metadata schema of B2FIND. Several key recommendations emerge from this example mapping exercise:

- To achieve as much richness in the metadata mapping as possible, our recommendation is that PaN providers should seek to map not only mandatory elements but also recommended and optional metadata elements.
- To increase interoperability and consistency, controlled vocabulary should be used wherever possible, especially for metadata types such as keyword and discipline.
- The use of PIDs and the related identifier metadata type offers the opportunity to improve findability and to link to other resources, perhaps including sample and instrument PID, if these were to be adopted widely by the PaN community in the future.
- The description metadata type should not be overlooked for its potential to provide valuable additional information, including about the methods and sample.
- The process of mapping the ExPaNDS framework to the B2FIND schema suggests that some potentially important metadata types may be missing from the ExPaNDS framework. As such, the PaN community may wish to add to and improve upon the current version of the ExPaNDS metadata framework, where experience and practice indicate this could be beneficial.

At present, each PaN provider interacts with B2FIND and OpenAIRE on an individual basis. The result is that different metadata mappings are produced by the different facilities. While over time, we might expect the adoption of ExPaNDS metadata framework to lead to more consistency in these mappings, it is likely that local practices and policies will still result in some ongoing differences.

NOTE: a mapping table between B2FIND names and the ExPaNDS framework from fig. 3 is suggested in ExPaNDS D2.7, chapter 3, page 60.

Theme 3: Derived data provenance and preservation

Provenance and preservation

Provenance addresses the question of **how an artefact has come into existence**. In this context provenance is therefore centred on strategies to capture information about software environment (dependencies), parameters and workflows leading to the obtention of derived data. **Preservation** is more concerned about how to ensure that an artefact will still be usable in the long term.

In both cases, correctly referencing / citing software is of prime importance for FAIR. The [FAIR Principles for Research Software](https://fair4rs.org/)²⁰ (abbreviated **FAIR4RS**) should be consulted whenever this is the case, as well as the the **software citation principles**²¹ designed in 2016 by the [FORCE11](https://force11.org/)²² working group. According to them, several quality criteria have to be fulfilled whenever citing software:

- Credit and attribution
- Unique identification
- Persistence
- Accessibility
- Specificity

Regarding which metadata are important for capturing derived data provenance after processing / analysis, the use of tools relying on the [PROV](https://www.w3.org/TR/prov-o/)²³ ontology (PROV-O) can be helpful to provide PaN facility users with graphical summaries of workflows. PROV is the W3C standard supporting the interchange of provenance information. PROV-O specifies the three following classes (Figure 5):

- **Entities:** representing an “object”: i.e document, data, website
- **Agents:** person or software performing an activity
- **Activities:** process that makes use of an entity and/or generates a new entity

Fig 5: diagram of the three PROV-O classes and their relations (properties) ²⁴.

²⁰

<https://rd-alliance.org/group/fair-research-software-fair4rs-wg/outcomes/fair-principles-research-software-fair4rs-0>

²¹ Smith AM, Katz DS, Niemeyer KE, FORCE11 Software Citation Working Group. (2016) Software Citation Principles. PeerJ Computer Science 2:e86. DOI: 10.7717/peerj-cs.86 <https://peerj.com/articles/cs-86/>

²² <https://force11.org>

²³ <https://www.w3.org/TR/prov-overview/>

²⁴ <https://www.w3.org/TR/2013/REC-prov-o-20130430/>

The responsibility properties are shown in pink

Other semantic models such as PREMIS²⁵ (Preservation Metadata Implementation Strategies) also exists to handle **preservation** aspects. PREMIS has been designed to be easily encoded in XML. The associated **data dictionary** defines **semantic units and subunits**, each of which corresponds to a preservation metadata element (e.g. objectIdentifier, storageMedium, format, etc). These semantic units can be seen as **properties of the five following entities** forming the base of the PREMIS data model (fig.12) :

- **Objects** (discrete units of digital information, e.g. a file)
- **Intellectual entities** (e.g. some chunk of data)
- **Events** (something that happens at a point in time, e.g. file creation)
- **Agents** (person, organisation that perform events, thereby affecting objects)
- **Rights** (permissions, copyright etc)

Practical recommendations

- For experiments, document:
 - the **firmware version** of the instrument(s)
 - any **processing activities** that might have happened before writing the raw data to disk (e.g. data reduction)
- For any kind of processing or analysis, document:
 - the **software environment** (if virtual machines or containers were used this could be a link/reference to download the image that was used)
 - the **exact version of any 3rd party software/code** (i.e. anything that is not written by the researcher) that was used (if open-source a link/reference to the version of the source code is recommended)
 - A representation of the data processing/analysis **workflow** if applicable
 - for code that is written by the researcher, consider **applying the FAIR4RS** principles
- If provenance data is to be recorded, consider using the **W3C PROV standard**. When deciding the level of granularity for documenting the activities, we recommend documenting non-human interrupted/involved steps as a single activity. Steps where human interaction is involved, are recommended to be documented as separate activities.

²⁵ <https://www.loc.gov/standards/premis/>

Sustainability of the FAIR metadata framework

The ExPaNDS metadata framework for FAIR data is a first attempt to produce a unified and FAIR-compliant approach regarding the choice and the structure of the metadata to collect all along the PaN data lifecycle. While some fields are clearly defined, others such as “sample information” or “preservation” information are loosely defined so that concerted initiatives will have to be undertaken in the future in order to reach inter-facilities standards for such descriptions.

It thus is desirable that the framework, its definitions and modalities of implementation get maintained and updated regularly well beyond the ExPaNDS project. An option to consider would be the creation of a permanent committee integrated in the management of all facilities, in charge of addressing these questions in depth so as to promote and adopt common practices among PaN RIs regarding FAIR metadata.

The text of this Guidance Note has been prepared by Nicolas Soler (ALBA synchrotron) and is mainly based *on the following ExPaNDS documents*:

ExPaNDS D2.2: *Draft Recommendations for FAIR Photon and Neutron Data Management*. Salvat, D., Gonzalez-Beltran, A., Görzig, H. et al. (2020). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4312825>

ExPaNDS D2.7: *Final recommendations for FAIR Photon and Neutron Data Management*. Soler, N., McBirnie, A., Gonzalez-Beltran, A., Vukolov, A., Minotti, C., et al. 2022, July 7. <https://zenodo.org/record/6799105>

ExPaNDS D3.2: *ExPaNDS ontologies v1.0*. Collins, Ramos, da G., Iyayi, Görzig, Beltrán, G., et al. 2021, June 4. <https://zenodo.org/record/4806026>

ExPaNDS D3.3: *Report on status, gap analysis and roadmap towards harmonised and federated metadata catalogues for EU national Photon and Neutron RIs*. Ashton, Ramos, D. G., & Gonzalez-Beltran. 2020, October 31. <https://zenodo.org/record/4146819>

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Appendix: Mapping the metadata framework to NeXus base classes

	Framework field	Possible NeXus class/field
Proposal	PI/Main proposer	NXuser/[name, ORCID, role="principal_investigator"]
	Co-investigators	NXuser/[name, ORCID, role=""co_investigator"]
	Sample description	NXsample
	Experiment description	NXentry/experiment_description
	Facility information	NXsource/name
	Proposal identifier	NXentry/experiment_identifier
Scheduling	Sample preparation	NXsample/[preparation_date, description]
Experiment	Visiting experimental team (user id)	NXuser/[facility_user_id, ORCID]
	Experiment date	NXentry/[start_time, end_time]
	Sample information	NXsample
	Instrument information	NXinstrument, OR NXnote (software etc) OR NXentry/program_name
	Calibration information	NXdetector/[calibration_date, angular_calibration_applied, angular_calibration[i, j], calibration_method]
	Experimental planning	NXentry/experiment_description OR NXnote
	Environmental parameters	NXinstrument
	Laboratory notebook	NXnote
	Instrument scientist	NXuser/role="local_contact"
	[Experimental report]	NXentry/[experiment_documentation, notes]
Storage	Persistent Identifiers (PIDs)	NXentry/entry_identifier_uuid
	Preservation description information	NXnote
	Dataset information	NXentry/[collection_identifier, collection_description]
	File identifier	NXentry/entry_identifier
	[Representation information]	NXnote
	[Instrument parameters]	NXinstrument

Table 2: Mapping between the metadata framework and NeXus base classes for raw data

	Framework field	Possible NeXus class/field
Data processing	Processing team (user ID)	NXuser/[name, ORCID, role=""data processing"]
	Original data	NXprocess/parameters/raw_data
	Data format (after processing)	NXprocess/NOTE
	Dataset information	NXentry/[collection_identifier, collection_description]
	Processing information	NXprocess/NOTE
	Software package information	NXprocess/[program, version]
Data processing /analysis	Analysis team (user id)	NXuser/[name, ORCID, role=""data processing"]
	Original data	E.g. NXtomoproc/raw_data
	Software package information	NXprocess/[program, version]
	Dependence tracking and workflow	NXprocess/[NOTE, sequence_index]
	Data formats (after analysis)	NXprocess/NOTE
	Dataset information	NXentry/[collection_identifier, collection_description]
	File identifier	NXentry/[entry_identifier_uuid, entry_identifier]
	[Instrument parameters]	NXinstrument
	[Calibration information]	NXdetector/[calibration_date, angular_calibration_applied, angular_calibration[i, j], calibration_method]

Table 3: Mapping between the metadata framework and NeXus base classes for processed data